

ENGLISH IN INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation:

Based on etymology, lexical material from international borrowings and the rapid development of information technologies, make possible to study and analyze the importance of the terminological potential of the English language in the field of ICT and emphasizes the importance of studying modern trends in the emergence and implementation of new ICT terms in the scientific-technical field and the information space.

Key words: *ICT, blending, PC, compounding, automation.*

The modern world of high technology could not have come about without the invention of the computer. Computers are used throughout society for the storage and handling of data—from secret governmental files to banking transactions to private household accounts. Computers have opened up a new era in manufacturing through the techniques of automation, and they have enhanced modern communication, systems. They are essential tools in almost every field of research and applied technology, from the construction of models of the universe to the production of tomorrow's weather reports, and their use has in itself opened up new areas of conjecture. Database services and computer networks make available a great variety of information sources.

Computers come in a wide range of sizes. Supercomputers analyze massive, complexly interrelated sets of data. For example, they solve problems in aerodynamic design of supersonic aircraft, predict the weather, and come up with new designs for disease-specific drugs. Mainframe computers and their smaller cousins, minicomputers, are the workhorses of commerce and industry. These centralized machines maintain records, calculate payrolls, and analyze statistics, among many other jobs.

Compounding - joining two or more existing words together to make one word. The term *c o u c h s u r f i n g* (and related forms *couch surf*, *couch surfer*) meaning travelling on a budget, using a broad network of contacts in order to get overnight accommodation for free first appeared in 2004 with the launch of website

www.CouchSurfing.org, the brainchild of American web consultant, Casey Fenton. Although the capitalized variants CouchSurfing and CouchSurfer are registered trademarks of the website, the lower case variants, either as open or closed compounds, are now regularly used. And also in education teachers use www.create.cahoot.it play interactive games with students. The name of the site was originated from the aim of the online site. Teachers create quiz-questions beforehand every lesson in order to make the lesson more interesting.

Abbreviations: Acronyms or Initialisms Acronyms and initialisms are both abbreviations made from the first letters of a group of words, the former are said as a single word while the latter are spelt out. There is a tendency in the present world to use abbreviations as self-dependent words and replacement of expressions by another more simple and understandable combination of words and letters. Acronyms An acronym *w y s i w y g* (meaning 'what you see is what you get') in this case it's not spelt as it sounds.

Initialisms are widely spread among ICT terms. Starting from WWW World Wide refers to all the public websites or pages that users can access on their local computers and other devices through the Internet. These pages and documents are interconnected by means of hyperlinks that users click on for information. Some words aren't really acronyms, but are just shortened versions that are quicker and easier to say, such as 'hi-tech' for high technology. As for, *w i- f i* - wireless fidelity - sometimes it is written with a hyphen, sometimes not. It is an implementation of IEEE wireless communication standard 802.11. Technically, it's standard ensuring that equipment works on a wireless network. It's an analogy with 'h i- f i', for high fidelity, that used to be common for recording some years ago. It's an interesting usage because it shows the return of a word that everybody thought had gone completely out of date - 'wireless'. It's used now for all sorts of applications - TV remotes can be talked about as wireless, if you control your garage door, it's a wireless control, mobile phones are sometimes referred to as wireless and GPS, satellite things in your car. Has a lot of associated terminology, of course, *wi-fi* is just one word of many that has come into usage in the last few years talking about the way in which we cope with the Internet. Have a look at F A Qs, you've seen them a thousand times on computer screens (they are computer text files containing a list of questions and answers, especially basic stuff on newsgroups where you want to find a quick reply). Basically URL means Uniform Resource Locator which is Web address from 1994. In the means of Internet terms HTTP is formed from Hyper Text Transfer Protocol.

Conversion - using a word from one part of speech in another part of speech. Although S M S is an English abbreviation, the more common word in everyday use is

text. This is a new word that has undergone a further change, by acquiring a new part of speech. So the noun *t e x t* has taken on a specific new meaning relating to mobile phones, and then has also become a verb. This is a very common phenomenon in language change when words acquire new functions, sometimes without even changing their spelling, that's why practically each described computer term undergo this way.

Blending - mixing words together, using parts of them These words that already exist in the language also team up in new ways to describe new inventions: Emoticon = emotion + icon (a visual character or sign which indicates emotion e.g. :) Ezine = electronic + magazine (a magazine that only exists on the Internet) Hacktivist = hack + activist (a person who changes or manipulates information on the Internet in order to convey a political message) Screenager = screen + teenager (a young person who spends a lot of time using a computer) Spyware = spy + software (a type of computer programme to get information from someone else's computer system illegally) Webcam = camera + World Wide Web (a video camera that transmits over the Internet).

Affixation - adding suffixes or prefixes to existing words. Prefixes New technical terms are often a rather pleasing combination of ancient and modern. Prefixes like multi- or nano- that come from Latin or Greek, are combined with new words. The word byte was a truly new word made up in the 1960s, but since then it has been combined with Greek prefixes like giga- and kilo- or tera- (meaning 'monster' represents a factor of 10¹²). The use of a single letter prefix with a hyphen is unusual, but not for computing such prefixes as e- and i- gave a birth to a vast majority of widely used set expressions.

In general, it is easy to learn to use Internet services. The worst problems of Internet illiteracy are, in addition to lack of economic resources of course, wrong attitudes. Older people are usually not accustomed to live in a world of continuous and rapid change, and they may not realize the importance of the Internet or the easiness of learning to use it.

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